

2) For KBo 33.175+, see M. Salvini & I. Wegner *SMEA* 24: 182 and L. Mascheroni *SMEA* 24: 157. For KBo 23.28, see M. Salvini & I. Wegner, *ChS* I/4: 4 (‘Als Schreiber für die 2.Tafel [KBo 23.28 w.w.] kommt, wegen des zum Teil erhaltenen Titels GAL.DJUB.SAR. MES in Text Nr. 2, lk. Rand 1’, der sich auf den Grossvater bezieht, nur Hulanabi in Frage’).

3) Note that a Hulanabi is also mentioned as the teacher of NU.GIŠ.SAR in KUB 44.61 (CTH 461).

4) See the dissertation of W. Waal, University of Leiden.

5) Note that Salvini & Wegner *SMEA* 24: 182 and Mascheroni *SMEA* 24: 157 join KBo 33.175 and ABoT 2 indirectly to KUB 32.100. The *Konkordanz*, however, joins the latter fragment indirectly to KBo 35.262 and KBo 33.182 (CTH 628).

6) Salvini & Wegner, *SMEA* 24: 182 n. 20.

Willemijn WAAL, w.waal@hum.leidenuniv.nl, Leiden University, LIAS

82) A Wanderwort? – In my recently published note “Akkadian Cognates to Some Ugaritic Words”, *SEL* 25, 2008, 57-62 (pp. 57 and 62), I commented on Akkadian equivalents to Ug. *apy*, “baker”. It derives, of course, from the Ug. verb *apy*, “to bake”, which is Semitic and has cognates in Aramaic, Ethiopic, Hebrew, Old South Arabian, Phoenician and Syriac (cf. HALOT, 78; DNWSI, 94-95). Three additional comments can be made.

(1) It should also have been mentioned there that Egyptian *ipt* (written ‘*i=pa₂=ta*’), a noun meaning “cakes, biscuits”, does seem to be a loan from Semitic. For discussion cf. J. E. Hoch, *Semitic Words in Egyptian Texts of the New Kingdom and Third Intermediate Period* (Princeton 1994) pp. 21-22 §7. It is also listed in L. H. Lesko, *A Dictionary of Late Egyptian*, Vol. 1 (Providence 2002) 25.

(2) Curiously, Hurrian *ephe* means “oven”, as documented in E. Neu, *Das hurritische Epos der Freilassung I. Untersuchungen zu einem hurritisch-hethitischen Textensemble aus Ḫattuša* (StBoT 32: Wiesbaden 1996) p. 167 and p. 429 n.70 and by J. Catsanicos, “L’apport de la bilingue de Ḫattuša à la lexicologie hourrite”, in J.-M. Durand, ed., *Amuru I* (Paris 1996) 197-296, on p. 216 §4.5, p. 238 §9.2 and p. 278b. It occurs in KBo XXXII Nr. 14 rev. IV 9-10, 23 (text and translation Neu, *op. cit.*, pp. 84 and 86) and corresponds to UDUN, “oven”, in the Hittite section of the bilingual, unfortunately with no spelling (cf. CHD Š, 105a). Whether it is a loan from Semitic – cf. also Akk. *nēpītu*, “baker’s trough or oven” (CAD N/2, 170-171) or “baking trough” (CDA, 250), “Backtrog” (AHw, 779a) – is uncertain.

(3) Somewhat more remotely, Hitt. *ḫapn-* / *ḫappen-*, “baking kiln, fire-pit, broiler (oven)” (A. Kloekhorst, *Etymological Dictionary of the Hittite Inherited Lexicon*, Leiden 2008, 297-298) may also belong to this family of terms for “oven”¹⁾. The Greek equivalent ‘*optaō*, “to bake”, from Greek ‘*optos*, “baked” (cf. J. Puhvel, *Hittite Etymological Dictionary*, vol. 3: *Words Beginning with H*, Berlin - New York 1991, 121-122), indicates the root to be **h₃ep-* (cf. Kloekhorst, *op. cit.*, 298)²⁾.

Unless due to coincidence, these correspondences seem to suggest that the set of words for “oven” and “to bake” may be Wanderwörter with an ancient history. Similarly, J. Greppin calls another word for “oven” – found in Indo-European, Semitic, Egyptian, Kartvelian, Daghestani, Berber and Turkic – “a world-champion loanword”³⁾.

1) For the comparison with Hurrian see A. Fournet – A. R. Bomhard, *The Indo-European Elements in Hurrian* (La Garenne Colombes/Charleston 2010) 111.

2) See also D. M. Weeks, *Hittite Vocabulary: An Anatolian Appendix to Buck’s Dictionary of Selected Synonyms in the Principal Indo-European Languages* (unpub. Ph.D. thesis, University of California 1985) p. 20 §1.82.

3) J. A. C. Greppin, “A Note on the Etymology of Old Egyptian *TRR*”, *Chronique d’Égypte* 68, 1993, 9-11.

W.G.E. WATSON (08-09-2010) wilfwatson@talktalk.net,
11 Park Drive, MORPETH, NE61 2SY (GRANDE-BRETAGNE)

83) New proposals of family relationship at Nuzi based on HSS 19 134 and 19 86* – M. M. Morrison, in her study on Nuzi eastern archives (*SCCNH* 4 [1993], 3-130), analyzes among other aspects the family of Ar-tura, son of Kuššiya (47-65). Her study and conclusions on the family of Uḫap-tae, son of Ar-tura, are determined by a very specific reconstruction of the familial situation shown by HSS 19 134. In our opinion, this interpretation has some flaws, which we correct by presenting an alternative genealogy for Uḫap-tae’s family.

The origin of HSS 19 134 is unknown, although it could had been found originally in the so-called Group 17, situated in the eastern part of the site, where the archive of Ar-tura was located (*SCCNH* 4, 47-48). The beginning of the document says:

¹⁾EME-šu ša ^m[kār-ra]-te ²⁾DUMU pu-i-ta-e ³⁾a-na pa-ni LÚ.MEŠ ⁴⁾ši-bu-ti iq-ta-bi ⁵⁾DUMU.SAL-šú ša ^mut-ḫap-ta-e DUMU ar-tù-ra ⁶⁾ù ^fa-ze-e aš-ša-ti-ia ⁷⁾i+na tù-li-mi-šu ⁸⁾[ur-te]-eb-bi-šu-mi.

Morrison (*SCCNH* 4, 50) proposes as its translation: «The statement which Karrate, son of Pui-tae spoke before witnesses: “The daughter of Uḫap-tae son of Ar-tura, ^fAze, my wife, I have lain with her...”. According to this reading, ^fAze was the daughter of Uḫap-tae (see the explanations in pp. 49, 57, 121, and the genealogies in pp. 52, 116). The same idea is assumed by other authors (J. M. Breneman, *Nuzi Marriage Tablets*, Brandeis Univ. Ph.D. 1971, 183; E. Cassin/J.-J. Glassner, *Anthroponymie et anthropologie de Nuzi*, Malibu 1977, 39a).

On the other hand, J. Fincke (*SCCNH* 7 [1995], 9) interprets the text in a different way: «Aussage des Qarrāde, des Sohnes des Pui-tae. Vor Zeugen hat er (folgendermaßen) erklärt: “Die Tochter des Uḫap-tae, des Sohnes des Artura, hat Azie, meine Ehefrau, an ihrer Brust aufgezogen”. Instead of Wilhelm’s proposal for l. 7

(*i+na tû-li-i*¹(copy: MI)-šû; see J. Fincke, *SCCNH* 7, 8 n. 5), we can also read this part as *i+na tû-li-mi-šû* (*ina tulī ummīšû*, “from the breast of her¹ mother”), idea argued by K. Deller and W. R. Mayer (“Akkadische Lexikographie: CAD M”, *OrNS* 53 [1984], 106) and accepted by M. Stol (*Birth in Babylonia and the Bible. Its Mediterranean Setting*, CM 14, Groningen 2000, 183). In any case, we fully agree with Fincke’s interpretation of the document, according to whom ¹Aze and the “daughter of Uṭḫap-tae” are two different persons.

Who is the “daughter of Uṭḫap-tae” mentioned in HSS 19 134: 5? The key lies behind a marriage adoption contract written earlier, HSS 19 86, concerning the same family. Although according to the excavation report this document was found in the palace (N 120), it could have actually belonged to Uṭḫap-tae’s familial archives, placed in the eastern part of the site (consequently to Group 17. See other confusions on this archive N 120 in M. M. Morrison, *SCCNH* 4, 19 n. 35).

The text states: ¹*tup-p[ī ma]-[ar-tū]-ti [ša]* ²*[m]k[ār-r]a-te DUMU pu-i-[ta-e]* ³*D[UMU.SAL]-sū [nu-ru-ma-tu₄ TU[R-i]* ⁴*[i+na] tû-li-ū a-na ma-ar-tu-ti* ⁵*[a-n]a^{mut-ḫap-ta-e} DUMU ar-[t]u-ra* ⁶*[i]t-ta-din [ū]* ^{mut-ḫap-t[a]-[e]} ⁶*[nu-ru-ma-tu₄ [ū-ra]-ab-bá-aš* ⁸*[a-na] aš-šū-ti [i-na]-[an-di]n ù KÛ.BABBAR.MEŠ-[šū]* ⁹*[il-le]-[eq-qè]*.

The proposed translation is: «Table[t of dau]g[hte]rsh[ip] [of] K[ar]rate, son of Pui-[tae]. [He has gi]ven his d[au]ghter ¹Nūru-mātu, a [su]ckling child (lit. “a child from the breast[s]”), as daughter [t]o Uṭḫap-tae, son of Ar-[t]ura. [And] Uṭḫap-[t]a[e] shall ra[ise] ¹Nūru-mātu (and) [he shall g]ive (her) away [as] wife and [ta]ke her¹ silver».

In our opinion, the chronological order of the events described in the texts is: (1) Karrate gives in daughtership his biological daughter ¹Nūru-mātu to Uṭḫap-tae (HSS 19 86: 3-6); (2) Uṭḫap-tae shall raise her, and since she is a suckling girl, he must hire a wet nurse (HSS 19 86: 6-7); (3) Uṭḫap-tae hires a certain ¹Aze, the biological mother of the girl and wife of Karrate, as wet nurse (HSS 19 134: 6-7). Since ¹Nūru-mātu legally becomes Uṭḫap-tae’s adopted daughter, Karrate refers to her as “daughter of Uṭḫap-tae” (HSS 19 134: 5).

Note that the only examples from Nuzi with the expression *ina tulī=šû*, “from her¹ breasts”, are found in both documents HSS 19 86 and 134, being referred to the same girl, ¹Nūru-mātu (as G. van Driel and R. M. Jas think, see M. Stol, CM 14 [2000], 183 n. 78. Note also in HSS 19 86: 4 the form *[i+na] tû-li-ū* instead of their reading *ina tu-le-e*). Regarding this expression, see other parallels in the Late Old Babylonian text BBVOT 1 23: 18 (*i-na tu-le-e(-)em*, cf. C. Wilcke, AOAT 247 [1997], 417), in the akkadian text from Ugarit RS 17.155: 23’ (*ina tu-le-e-i-šû*) and, with other words but same sense, in the Neo-Assyrian document ND 5463: 6 (TA* UGU *zi-i-zi*, note the misspelling *zi-zi-i* in K. Radner SAAS 6 [1997], 131 n. 662; editio princeps in B. Parker, *Iraq* 19 [1957], 133 and pl. XXXII; cf. also R. Whiting, SAA 12 [1995], 120 no. 95).

Due to these circumstances, it is understood from HSS 19 134: 9-12 that Uṭḫap-tae pays to Karrate the *teḫambašḫu* or fees for the raising of a child (J. Fincke, *SCCNH* 7 [1995], 6-12; H. Schneider-Ludorff, *SCCNH* 18 [2009], 488). In this way it is ascertained that between the adoption (HSS 19 86) and the payment of the *teḫambašḫu* (HSS 19 134) some time went by, aspect which we have pointed out for JEN 571 / BM 80388 being based on other evidences (D. Justel, *SCCNH* 20 [2010], § 2.4).

All this information is useful for redoing Uṭḫap-tae’s family tree, and for proposing the following familial relations from HSS 19 86 and 19 134:

*) This work has been carried out thanks to a pre-doctoral scholarship granted by the Government of Spain (FPU, ref. AP2006-04723). I am very grateful to B. Lion (Université de Tours) and J.-P. Vita (IEIOP-CSIC, Zaragoza) for their reading and comments on the note.

Daniel JUSTEL (27-5-2010) djstel@gmail.com
 Instituto de Estudios Islámicos y del Oriente Próximo (CSIC), c/ Diputados, 19-21, 50004, ZARAGOZA (SPAIN)

84) Multābiltu Commentaire 4 – Une édition de ce texte est offerte dans U. Koch, *Secrets of Extispicy*, AOAT 326, Munster 2005, n° 28.

Dans le but d’obtenir un texte aussi complet que possible, U. Koch réunit bout à bout plusieurs manuscrits. Sur les neuf manuscrits retenus, le dernier I, est à écarter ; il ne présente aucun lien avec les autres, tout au plus peut-on y voir, aux lignes 3’-4’, un commentaire d’une ligne du manuscrit F ii 6’. Les manuscrits B, F et H, les mieux